

Supplementary Information

Modulating the Pro-apoptotic Activity of Cytochrome *c* at a Biomimetic Electrified Interface

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Supporting Movie S1: Molecular dynamics simulation of Cyt *c* at a negative bias at the aqueous|organic interface.

Supporting Movie S2: Molecular dynamics simulation of Cyt *c* at a positive bias at the aqueous|organic interface.

Section S1 Characterisation of Cyt *c* films by fluorescence and confocal Raman microscopy

UV/vis-TIR spectra show that a blue-shift of the Soret and Q bands was observed only at positive biasing in the presence of TB⁻ (Fig. 2B), and demonstrate a partial loss or relaxation of the tertiary structure of Cyt *c* (62).

200 μL of a 200 μM LiTB aqueous solution was added to a PBS aqueous phase at pH 7 containing 10 mM Cyt *c*. TB⁻ salts are barely soluble in aqueous solutions (concentrations below 1 mM must be employed), but they are soluble enough to promote the precipitation of Cyt *c* by electrostatic interactions with TB⁻ species (see Fig. S1). The addition of LiTB salts to the aqueous phase is different to the experiments shown in Fig. 2, wherein LiTB was added to the organic phase to set the Galvani potential difference across the interface ($\Delta_o^w \phi$).

The precipitates shown in Fig. S1 were collected and characterised by confocal fluorescence microscopy.

Fig. S1. The addition of TB⁻ anions to the aqueous phase induces the spontaneous precipitation of denatured Cyt *c* species. These deposits were collected and characterised by confocal fluorescence microscopy. Photo Credit: Alonso Gamero-Quijano (University of Limerick, Ireland).

In the native state, the fluorescence emission of cytochrome species is low due to the quenching of the emission signal. However, a partial unfolding of the protein decreases the fluorescence quenching, and the emission intensity of Tryptophan-59 becomes measurable (63). The collected Cyt *c* precipitates presented an evident emission intensity indicating that the strong interaction between Cyt *c* and TB⁻ added in an aqueous solution should affect the Cyt *c* native structure.

Fig. S2. Phase contrast image (Olympus BX 51 with a 10-x lens) of the film formed at the interface using (A) 100 μM and (B) 500 μM KTB in the organic phase. Aqueous phase: 20 μM Cyt *c* in 10 mM PBS, pH 7.1. (C) Raman spectra of Cyt *c* films shown in panel A. These films were formed during a positive biasing using 100 μM (black line) and 500 μM (red line) KTB.

The morphology of a Cyt *c* film formed at the aqueous|organic interface is clearly affected by the concentration TB^- species dissolved in the organic phase as shown in Fig. S2A-B. *In situ* confocal Raman microscopy of these Cyt *c* films at given concentrations of KTB has shown that the presence of large concentrations of TB^- in the organic phase and the positive biasing set by Li^+ cations partitioning accelerate the formation of a visible film that shows an upshift of the core size marker bands ν_4 , ν_2 and ν_{10} (see Table S1 below) due to the presence of TB^- near the interface (28). The frequency upshifts of $\sim 4\text{-}5\text{ cm}^{-1}$ reflect the structural changes of the heme pocket supporting our findings by UV/vis-TIR spectroscopy (29).

Table S1. Cyt *c*'s core size markers in the absence and presence of TB^- species

Core size marker	Raman shift / cm^{-1}		
	20 μM Cyt <i>c</i> in phosphate buffer	Cyt <i>c</i> film 100 μM KTB	Cyt <i>c</i> film 500 μM KTB
ν_4	1370	1374	1374
ν_2	1583	1587	1588
ν_{10}	1636	1638	1640

Section S2 Estimation of the interfacial aqueous and organic electrolyte distributions for molecular dynamics modelling

Fig. S3. Differential capacitance measurements (A) in the absence and (B) in the presence of Cyt *c* species using electrochemical cell 1 (see Fig. 5).

Differential capacitance measurements are closely related to the charging processes occurring at the aqueous|organic interface in response to a perturbation potential. Also, these measurements reflect that charging processes at the interface at given potentials are different (see Fig. S3A). At more negative potentials, the aqueous side of the interface has a negative excess surface charge (anions). On the other hand, at more positive potentials, the aqueous side of the interface has a positive excess surface charge (cations). Furthermore, the differential capacitance depends on the cumulative excess of charge in the entire interfacial region, *i.e.*, the back-to-back diffusion layers. When a protein is adsorbed (Fig. S3B), the net charge of the protein modifies the charge distribution in the interfacial region, thereby changing the capacitance. Thus, these changes are taken as an indication of protein adsorption.

Fig. S4. Plots of the interfacial charge (q) vs. interfacial Galvani potential difference ($\Delta_0^w \phi$) estimated from the integration of the differential capacitance data presented in Fig. S4A-B. Here the potential of zero charge is the potential that sets the change of the net charge at the boundaries of the aqueous phase. From the PZC towards more positive potentials, the aqueous phase is charged positively, and the concentration of aqueous cations near the interface is greater than the bulk solution. On the other hand, from the PZC towards less positive potentials, the aqueous phase is charged negatively, and the concentration of aqueous anions near the interface is greater than the bulk aqueous phase.

The presence of Cyt *c* alters the differential capacitance measurements of the aqueous|organic interface, which signifies extensive restructuring of the interfacial region due to protein adsorption. The charge distribution was determined by the integration of the differential capacitance at a given potential (64). The progress of interfacial charging at positive and negative biasing in the absence (black curve) and presence of Cyt *c* (red curve) is shown in Fig. S4. From this data, to simulate the charging process at +0.5 V, we multiplied the bulk aqueous and organic electrolyte concentrations by a factor of 12.5 to reflect the measured interfacial concentrations (see dashed blue lines in Fig. S4). At +0.5 V, aqueous Na^+ and K^+ cations are used to balance the negative charge of the organic TB^- anions. On the other hand, to simulate the charging process at -0.2 V, we multiplied the bulk aqueous and organic electrolyte concentrations by a factor of 5.5 to reflect the measured interfacial concentrations (see dashed blue lines in Fig. S4). In this instance, H_2PO_4^- and HPO_4^{2-} anions balance the positive charge of BA^+ .

Section S3 Molecular dynamics model details and further analysis

S3.1 Model setup. The starting protein structure was obtained from the crystal structure of the oxidised form (Fe^{3+}) of Cyt *c* from bovine heart at 1.5 Å resolution (Protein Data Bank code 2B4Z (65)). To simulate neutral pH conditions, the protonation states of all residues in Cyt *c* were assigned from their estimated pK_a shifts at pH 7 using the Protein Preparation Wizard (66) in the Schrödinger Maestro (67) package to find the most favourable residue ionisation/tautomer states. All Lys, Arg and His33 residues were protonated, while His18 and His26 were kept neutral. A net charge of +9 was obtained in line with previous experimental findings (23). Water and organic solvent α,α,α -trifluorotoluene (TFT) molecules forming the aqueous|organic interface were placed in a rectangular box of dimensions 10 nm x 10 nm x 40 nm with each phase spanning a depth of 20 nm (see Fig. S5A) and full periodic boundary conditions applied to replicate the unit cell in all three directions. We modelled the effect of the biasing potentials by scaling the experimental ion distributions to mimic bias-induced creation of high local concentrations of ions at the interface at the sub- μs simulation timescales. At positive bias, the charged ions (positive in the water phase and negative in TFT) were added at 12.5 times their bulk concentrations, while at negative bias the charged ions (negative in water and positive in TFT) were added at 5.5 times their bulk concentrations (see section S2).

S3.2 Simulation protocol. Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations were performed with the Gromacs 2018.4 package using the CHARMM36m forcefield (68) with the aqueous phase containing the CHARMM-modified TIP3P (69) water molecules. The parameters for the oxidised state of the heme were obtained from ref. (70). The Cyt *c* is pulled slowly towards the interface by applying a harmonic constraint (force constant = 1000 kJ/mol/nm²) on the protein centre of mass. Cyt *c* protein and water molecule bond lengths to hydrogen were constrained using the LINCS (71) and the SETTLE (72) algorithms, respectively. An integration timestep of 2 fs was set using the leapfrog integrator (73), and coordinates were saved every 20 ps. Long-range electrostatics were treated by the Particle Mesh Ewald (PME) method (74). All systems were minimised for 10000 steps, and equilibrated and thermalised to 300K during 1 ns of constant volume dynamics followed by 1 ns at constant pressure of 1 bar and a time constant of 5 ps using the Berendsen barostat (75). All molecules were coupled separately in groups to an external heat bath with a coupling time constant of 1 ps using the Berendsen method (75). The production runs were carried out in triplicates (named run 0, repeat 1 and repeat 2) for 0.1 μs each (total runtime = 0.6 μs ; 2 biases x 3 repeats) in the constant pressure and temperature NPT ensemble. The run 0 at positive bias was further extended to 0.5 μs .

S3.3 Data processing, analysis, and visualisation. All analyses of density profiles, interaction distances, angles, numbers of contacts, solvent accessible surface areas and binding free energies (main text Fig. 3 and Figs. S5 – S15 below) were performed with Gromacs tools and trajectories were visualised using VMD (76). The fraction of native contacts Q (Fig. S5E) was calculated using the definition from Best, Hummer and Eaton (77), implemented in the MDTraj (78) python library, using the equation:

$$Q = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i,j} \frac{1}{1 + \exp[\beta(r_{ij}(t) - \lambda r_{ij}^0)]} \quad (\text{S1})$$

where N is the set of all pairs of heavy atoms (i, j) , and heavy atoms i and j are in contact if the distance between them is less than 5 Å and they are separated by at least 3 residues. $r_{ij}(t)$ is the distance between i and j in the structure sampled at time t and r_{ij}^0 is the distance in the starting structure at time 0. β is a smoothening parameter taken to be 5 Å⁻¹ and λ is a factor that describes fluctuations when the contact is formed, taken to be 1.8 for the all-atom model. For more details on the method and choice of parameter values, please see ref. (77).

The solvent-accessible surface area (SASA) of the part of Cyt c only exposed to water but not to TFT, was computed by estimating the difference between SASA of Cyt c and half the sum of contributions from SASA of Cyt c and ‘organic patch’, such that the surface accessibility area of Cyt c is measured relative to water only. Here, the organic patch considers any molecule in the organic phase that is within 4.0 Å of the Cyt c . The water ASA can then be given by the following equation:

$$SASA(Water) = SASA_{Cyt\ c} - SASA(TFT) \quad (\text{S2})$$

where,

$SASA(Water)$ = Solvent-accessible surface area of Cyt c in water

$SASA_{Cyt\ c}$ = Total solvent-accessible surface area of Cyt c

$SASA(TFT)$ = Solvent-accessible surface area of Cyt c in TFT

$$= 0.5 \times \left((SASA_{Cyt\ c} + SASA_{Organic\ patch}) - SASA_{Cyt\ c + Organic\ patch} \right) \quad (\text{S3})$$

such that,

$SASA_{Organic\ patch}$ = Solvent-accessible surface area of Cyt c in organic patch

$SASA_{Cyt\ c + Organic\ patch}$ = Solvent-accessible surface area of Cyt *c* and organic patch taken together

Similarly, to plot surface accessibility of Cyt *c* relative to TFT only (surface excess) and distinguish it from $SASA$ (*Water*), we compute the $SASA$ (*TFT*), which is given by Eqn. (S3) above.

The binding free energies (ΔG_{bind}) between TB^- (ligand) and Cyt *c* (receptor) were calculated using the molecular mechanics energies combined with Poisson-Boltzmann continuum solvation (MM/PBSA) (79) as implemented in Gromacs method *g_mmpbsa* (80):

$$\Delta G_{bind} = \Delta G_{bind,vacuum} + \Delta G_{solv,complex} - (\Delta G_{solv,ligand} + \Delta G_{solv,receptor}) \quad (S4)$$

$$\Delta G_{solv} = \Delta G_{polar} + \Delta G_{nonpolar} \quad (S5)$$

where $\Delta G_{bind,vacuum} = \Delta G_{MM}$ (MM = molecular mechanics energy = electrostatic energy + vdW energy in vacuum), $\Delta G_{solv,complex}$ = free energy of solvation of the Cyt *c*- TB^- complex, $\Delta G_{solv,ligand}$ = solvation energy of the TB^- , $\Delta G_{solv,receptor}$ = solvation free energy of Cyt *c*, ΔG_{polar} = polar solvation free energy or electrostatic component of solvation free energy, and $\Delta G_{nonpolar}$ = nonpolar solvation free energy approximated by the solvent accessible surface area (SASA) times a constant factor.

S3.4 Supplementary analysis. The main findings from the simulations and their relation to the experiments are described in the main text. Here, further details are provided for the interested reader. Input and output files of the molecular dynamics simulation data of Cyt *c* at pH 7 at the water|TFT interface may be accessed online through the Zenodo data repository at <https://zenodo.org/record/5044080#.YN4jPehKg2w>.

To further probe the possible partial-unfolding of Cyt *c* at the interface, we compare our computed structures to previous reports with model systems which identified three main Cyt *c* sites responsible for interaction with membrane phospholipids – A-site and two L-site (81). The A-site is thought to involve positively charged residues Lys72 and Lys73 for Cyt *c* recognition *via* electrostatic interactions with lipids (82), while the L-site (83) is believed to play a role in lipid binding *via* Lys22 and Lys25, and in apoptosis *via* Lys27, His26 and His33 (84). Although the C-site is also involved in lipid binding, it does not contain any positively charged residue, and forms hydrogen bonds with protonated acidic phospholipids *via* Asn52 in Cyt *c*. Our models reveal that only four (out of 21) positively-charged residues are involved in direct contact with TB^- at negative bias (Fig. S5F, left panel), which includes the A-site Lys72 and Lys73. Remarkably, as many as 15 positively-charged residues interact with TB^- at positive bias (Fig. S5F, right

panel), including A-site Lys 72 and Lys73, and Lys 22, Lys25, Lys27 and (neutral) His26 of the L-site. The computed time-averaged interaction maps (not shown) indicate that 71% of the positively-charged sites on Cyt *c* contact interfacial TB⁻ at positive bias, while only 19% are in contact at negative bias. Thus, by electrochemically controlling the ionic electrolyte distribution either side of Cyt *c*, we mimic *in vivo* Cyt *c*–lipid interactions by using positive bias to direct interfacial adsorption, orientation and partial opening of Cyt *c*.

We provide below an in-depth analysis of the timelines presented in Fig. 3 and Figs. S5, S7 – S15. The minimum distance of separation between the heme pocket and the interface was calculated as a function of time to account for the propensity of the heme active site to penetrate the interfacial layer (Fig. S5B) with stable close contacts far outweighing short-lived more dissociated states at positive bias (and the opposite trend evident at negative bias) during 0.1 μ s of dynamics. The angles sampled between the plane of the heme and interface (Fig. S5C) showed that at negative bias, the angle dropped steadily during the first \sim 30 ns as the heme pocket repeatedly reoriented before settling on a *quasi*-ordered orientation in water, always pointing away from the interface without any long-lived contacts. By contrast, positive biasing immediately creates a stable orientation of the heme plane perpendicular to the interface.

In Fig. S7, we show that the preferential orientational effect at positive bias is robust across the three independent MD runs at both biases. Fig. S7A shows that the heme pocket constantly reorients itself at negative biasing potential. During run 0, the heme reorients from 120° with respect to the interfacial plane during the first 30 ns, to sample tilts in the range of 30–60° for the remaining 70 ns. In repeat 1, the tilt angle remains consistent between 80–120° until 28 ns, after which it drops to 30° and stays below 60° until 58 ns before remaining at 80–100° until 0.1 μ s. Repeat 2 shows consistent tilt angles between 80–120° throughout the 0.1 μ s run. This heterogeneity in heme orientation across the three runs highlights the loose orientation of the heme pocket relative to the aqueous|organic interfacial plane at negative bias, contrary to the predominance of tight near-90° perpendicular orientation at positive bias (Fig. S7B). For all three runs at positive biasing potential, the heme pocket orients consistently at or near 90° (maximum range between 70–140°) throughout the 0.1 μ s runs and also throughout the extended run for 0.5 μ s (Fig. S11C, below). We obtain (Fig. S7D) sharp and dense peaks centered at 90° ranging between 70–120° for run 0, at 95° ranging between 70–120° for repeat 1 and at 100° for repeat 2 with a slightly wider distribution between 70–140°, with significant overlaps of densities between the three runs. This characteristic distribution of perpendicular orientation persists in the elongated 0.5 μ s run (Fig. S11D), with a narrow distribution centered at 96° ranging between 70–120°. By contrast, the densities at negative

bias (Fig. S7C) reveal bimodal distributions in 2 out of 3 runs, with two broad sub-populations of tilts near to 45 and 90°. The third run at negative bias shows a single peak at 94° with a wide distribution of 60–120°, highlighting the balance between biasing and local TB–Lys electrostatic interactions in determining the orientation, and so pre-organisation for electron transfer, of the heme pocket of Cyt *c* at the aqueous|organic interface. Thus, the MD data indicates a strong preference for perpendicular orientation of the heme pocket at the interface as stabilised by Lys binding to the TB⁻ scaffold that assembles at positive bias. This preferred orientation is consistently predicted across three independent 0.1 μs simulations and persists out to 0.5 μs of extended sampling. Our results agree with the literature where the perpendicular orientation of the Cyt *c* heme promotes electron transfer to a PEDOT layer or SAM-coated gold electrode, respectively (53, 54). At negative bias, this conformational preference is lost with a large population of non-perpendicular orientations sampled across the three 0.1 μs runs.

The steep decline in the protein fraction of native contacts (Q) at positive bias is consistent with an expected opening of Cyt *c* structure, while at negative biasing conformational change is slower (Fig. S5E). In Fig. S8A, the different rates of loss of fraction of native contacts Q for each run reveals the tendency of Cyt *c* to lose (and regain at times) native contacts randomly at negative bias without any propensity to form a stable structure: run 0 shows slow loss of contacts, repeat 1 attains some stability in Q until 95 ns after which there is abrupt and steep loss of contacts, while repeat 2 undergoes rapid loss of contacts, presenting conformationally diverse structures. By contrast, distinct plateaus in Q are consistently observed at positive bias (Fig. S8B), remaining stable out to 0.1 μs. The RMSD timelines (Fig. S8C-D) reflect the temporal changes in Q, showing large discrepancies between runs at negative bias but more consistent behaviour at positive bias. Fig. S8C shows most rapidly changing structural fluctuations for repeat 2 followed by run 0, while repeat 1 samples uniform conformation until 95 ns and then switches. On the other hand, similar to the native contacts, the RMSD trends at positive bias across all repeats reveal negligible structural deviation following initial relaxation (Fig. S8D), highlighting the stability of Cyt *c* at positive bias. Finally we consider the distribution of structurally similar clusters, based on the iterative RMSD clustering method using the GROMOS algorithm described by Daura *et al.* (85), and expressed as a function of cluster numbers ranked from most populated to least populated. Comparing Fig.S11 panels E and F, we observe that the evolution of cluster population with ranked clusters for all repeats at positive bias is overlapping and consistent, highlighting again the stability of Cyt *c* with least structural deviation compared to the negative bias. Fig. S10 shows the structural stability of Cyt *c* throughout the 0.5 μs of extended dynamics at positive bias, *via* evolution of RMSD (Fig. S10A), Q (Fig.

S10B), and distribution of structurally similar clusters (Fig. S10C). All three properties show persistence of structure from the 0.1 to 0.5 μs scale, providing support for the predicted protein conformational stability at positive bias.

At negative bias (Fig. S9A), more protein is exposed to water than at positive bias (Fig. 9B), which indicates that the protein tends to sit more into the organic phase at positive bias (Fig. S9C-D). This effect becomes more pronounced during the extended 0.5 μs run at positive bias (Fig. S11A-B). This effect is evident in the structure shown at 0.5 μs (Fig. S13B), where the heme pocket is partially submerged in the TB^- scaffold that assembles on the TFT side of the interface. Fig. S12A–C reveals the conformational diversity of Cyt *c* at negative bias, where three different orientations of the heme pocket with respect to the interface are identified from the most frequently sampled conformations of cluster ranked 1 in each of the three runs. This indicates that Cyt *c* does not adopt a preferential orientation at negative bias, but rather samples an ensemble of interconverting, degenerate conformations. On the other hand, the representative conformations at positive bias (Figs. S12D–F) identify a persistent, preferential conformation across all runs with a major population of the heme oriented normal to the interface. Similarly, this preferential conformational feature is maintained throughout the 0.5 μs of extended run 0 (see Fig. S13A).

To identify the positively-charged residues in Cyt *c* that interact with TB^- , we counted all instances where a Lys, His or Arg residue came within 0.45 nm of a TB^- molecule (Fig. S5F). Finally, to assess the binding affinities of TB^- anions to Cyt *c* at positive and negative biases, we computed the free energy of binding *via* the MM/PBSA method (described under **section S3.3 Data processing, analysis, and visualisation**). Multiple TB^- ions form strong, long-lived electrostatic contacts to Cyt *c* Lys residues during positive biasing, which is evident from a rapid improvement in ΔG_{bind} for all three repeats during the first 40 ns of dynamics, with strong binding maintained throughout the rest of the 0.1 μs trajectories (Fig. S14B). At negative bias (Fig. S14A), much weaker interactions are present. The corresponding energy distributions density reveal a broad range at negative bias with very low peak densities (Fig. S14C), which suggests weak, non-specific binding, whereas at positive bias (Fig. S14D), we see sharp and high peak densities of large negative ΔG_{bind} values (~ -750 kJ/mol) with positively skewed narrow distributions of -840 to -450 kJ/mol for run 0, -800 to -300 kJ/mol for repeat 1, and -800 to -360 kJ/mol for repeat 2, signifying strong and persistent binding of TB^- at positive bias.

To assess the relative contributions of Cyt *c* and individual TB^- molecules to the total binding free energy, we performed molecule-wise decomposition of the MM/PBSA free energy timelines (Fig. S15).

We observe that when studying a single TB^- ion binding to Cyt *c* at negative bias (Run 0 and Repeat 1 in Fig. S15 panel A and panel C, respectively), the contributions from both TB^- and Cyt *c* are at par with each other and follow a similar trend as a function of time, indicating that one TB^- molecule can bind to one Lys residue in Cyt *c* *via* weak electrostatic interactions. However, when studying the binding pattern of two TB^- anions with Cyt *c* (Fig. S15E), the energy contributions from the individual TB^- residues as a function of time follow different trends indicating that two TB^- molecules cannot bind consistently to Lys residues of Cyt *c* at negative bias. On the other hand, the profiles at positive bias (Figs. S15, B, D, F) show that multiple TB^- anions (three in total) bind much more favourably and persistently to Lys residues in Cyt *c* than at negative bias and remain bound for the duration of the 0.1 μs runs. We also mapped the binding profile of all the TB^- anions collectively with Cyt *c* at the water|TFT interface during the extended 0.5 μs run at positive bias (Fig. S15G). The simulations predict formation of a large-area, strongly-bound coat of anions which solidifies at the interface as more TB^- molecules migrate to the interface during the 0.5 μs of dynamics. The corresponding ΔG_{bind} energy distribution (Fig. S15H) shows a narrow distribution centered at -464 kJ/mol with time-averaged standard deviation of 15.5 kJ/mol, further highlighting the large-area, strong, and durable binding of TB^- to Cyt *c* at the positively biased aqueous|organic interface.

Fig. S5. Computed properties of this bias-induced pre-organisation of the liquid bio-interface. (A) Initial setup of systems for MD simulations at negative (left) and positive (right) biases showing the water (top; blue) and TFT (bottom; yellow) molecules in a 10 nm x 10 nm x 40 nm rectangular box. The bis(triphenylphosphoranylidene)ammonium tetrakis-(pentafluorophenyl)borate (BATB) BA⁺ and TB⁻ ions (in the TFT) are represented as blue and red shapes, respectively, while the Na⁺ and the K⁺ ions (in water) are shown as orange and cyan spheres, respectively. The anions HPO₄²⁻ and H₂PO₄⁻ are represented as spheres coloured according to atom types. The organic electron donor DcMfc is shown as a green shape. (B) Heme-interface distances as a function of time at the negative and positive biases. (C) Temporal evolution of the angles between the heme plane and the interfacial plane. (D) Time evolution of the minimum distance between TB⁻ and Lys residues in Cyt c. (E) Fraction of native contacts (Q) as a function of time. (F) The positively charged residues in Cyt c that make direct contacts with TB⁻ at the interface during negative (left inset) and positive (right inset) biasing. A-site residues are represented in green, while L-site residues are marked in blue. Note that L-site His26 is predicted to be neutral at pH 7 (see above) while His33 is protonated.

Fig. S6. Computed partial density profiles of solvents and important ionic species at negative bias for (A) repeat 1 and (B) repeat 2, and at positive bias for (C) repeat 1 and (D) repeat 2 MD simulations.

Fig. S7. Time evolution of tilt angle of the heme pocket in Cyt *c* at the aqueous|organic interfacial plane (A) at negative bias and (B) at positive bias, and the corresponding tilt angle distributions at negative (C) and positive (D) biases.

Fig. S8. Fraction of native contacts (Q) of Cyt *c* at (A) negative bias and at (B) positive bias, root mean square deviation (RMSD) of Cyt *c* heavy atomic positions at (C) negative and (D) positive biasing potentials, and distribution of structurally similar clusters(85) of Cyt *c* ranked from most to least populated at (E) negative and (F) positive biases.

Fig. S9. Solvent-accessible surface area (SASA) of Cyt *c* to Water (SASA (Water)) at (A) negative bias and at (B) positive bias, and SASA of Cyt *c* to TFT (SASA (TFT)) at (C) negative and (D) positive biases.

Fig. S10. The structural stability of Cyt *c* throughout the 0.5 μ s of extended dynamics at positive bias. (A) RMSD and (B) fraction of native contacts (Q) as a function of time, (C) distribution of cluster populations, and (D) computed partial density profiles of the solvents and ion species that modulate Cyt *c* conformation, at positive bias for the 0.5 μ s of extended sampling.

Fig. S11. Time evolution during 0.5 μ s of extended dynamics at positive bias of (A) SASA (Water) of Cyt c, (B) SASA (TFT) of Cyt c, and (C) tilt angle of the heme pocket. (D) shows the corresponding tight, perpendicular tilt angle distribution.

Fig. S12. Representative structure identified from conformational clustering analysis of RMSD for (A) run 0, (B) repeat 1 and (C) repeat 2 at negative bias, and for (D) run 0, (E) repeat 1 and (F) repeat 2 for positive bias, showing the interfacial TB^- anion scaffold that stabilises the active conformation of the heme at positive bias.

Fig. S13. Representative conformation of Cyt *c* at the water|TFT interface obtained from (A) RMSD cluster analysis (85) at positive bias across 0.5 μ s of dynamics, and (B) final conformation of Cyt *c* at 0.5 μ s. The downward-pointing, accessible heme moiety is shown as sticks with the surrounding protein shown in cartoon representation, and the scaffolding TB^- anions are shown as red sticks.

Fig. S14. Comparison of Cyt *c*-TB⁻ binding free energies (ΔG_{bind} ; normalised per molecule of TB⁻) during three simulations at (A) negative biasing potential and (B) positive biasing potential, and distributions of binding energies at (C) negative and (D) positive biases.

Fig. S15. Mapping of individual TB^- binding profiles across the three MD runs (0.1 μs each) at (A, C, E) negative and (B, D, F) positive biases, including decomposition of binding energies into contributions from Cyt *c* and the TB^- anions. (G) Computed Cyt *c*– TB^- binding free energies (ΔG_{bind} , per molecule of TB^-) during 0.5 μs extended simulation at positive bias. By the end of the 0.5 μs of dynamics, 38 molecules of TB^- stay at the interface (see Fig. S13B). (H) The corresponding tight distribution of calculated binding energies.

Section S4 Analyses using the peak current and potential for reversible and irreversible electrochemical transformations

S4.1 Analyses of cyclic voltammetry (CV) data. In a recent article, we have shown that electron transfer (ET) between Cyt *c* and DcMFC using a closed bipolar electrochemical cell (CBPEC) configuration with aqueous and organic electrolyte solutions is reversible (34). Therein, ET took place without conformational barriers, and the current recorded was on the order of 10^{-7} A (34). At the electrified aqueous|organic interface, additional barriers to interfacial electron transfer (IET) between aqueous Cyt *c* and organic DcMFC.

We would like to clarify that in conventional electrochemistry (*i.e.*, 3-electrode configuration) Cyt *c* could be considered an inner-sphere redox probe since specific interactions with the electrode surface are needed. This behaviour is due to the affinity of Cyt *c* to the electrode surface (86–89). Hypothetically assuming that Cyt *c* can accept electrons from bare metallic electrodes, according to Marcus theory (90), the heterogeneous electron transfer with metallic substrates will demand the lowest reorganisation energy ($\lambda=20.35$ kJ·mol⁻¹) compared to semiconductors or aqueous|organic interfaces. Closed bipolar configurations use metallic electrodes as electron bridges interconnecting the aqueous and organic containers. Therefore, in bipolar configurations, the energy band known as the Fermi level is easily modulated by external biasing.

At aqueous|organic interfaces, external biasing changes the interfacial boundaries, thereby changing the reorganisation energies of the donor-acceptor species of each phase, and the local concentration of electrolytes near the interface (91). Both changes alter the electrochemical potential of the redox reaction in solution, effectively altering the driving force for electron transfer by changing the energy (potential) difference across the L|L interface. Thus, IET at aqueous|organic interfaces occurs between the HOMO level of the electron donor and the LUMO level of the electron acceptor. This IET transfer event will occur at a certain distance, potential, and specific interfacial distribution within the interface created between the organic and aqueous phases. According to the Marcus theory applied to aqueous|organic interfaces (92, 93), IET will demand the highest solvent reorganisation energy ($\lambda = 43.93$ kJ·mol⁻¹), which is almost the double energy needed compared to metallic electrodes. This simple comparison of reorganisation energies suggests that despite the similarity between biphasic closed bipolar electrode configurations and aqueous|organic systems, the former must be taken as a qualitative reference to determine the probability and potential region where IET reactions occur.

Hypothetically if Cyt *c* was reduced by DcMFC then currents $<10^{-7}$ A should be expected (34). However, the CVs presented in Fig. 4B, C & E show an irreversible IET process at a positive potential with currents on the first CV cycle $> 5 \times 10^{-5}$ A (a near 50-fold increase in magnitude compared with the CBPEC configuration for the same biphasic system).

To explain this 50-fold increase in current, firstly, the local concentration of Cyt *c* near the interface was estimated by analysis of the peak current (i_p) for an irreversible system (36, 37):

$$i_p = (2.99 \times 10^5) (n[(1 - \alpha)n]^{\frac{1}{2}} D^{\frac{1}{2}} C A v^{\frac{1}{2}}) \quad (\text{S6})$$

with the constant 2.99×10^5 given in $\text{C} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{V}^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, the diffusion coefficient of Cyt *c* (D) = $11.8 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (35), $n = 1$ for a one electron-transfer process, the aqueous|organic interfacial surface area (A) = 1.53 cm^2 , and $\alpha = 0.5$. Using Equation S6, the concentration of Cyt *c* near the interface was estimated as ca. 1 mM, *two orders of magnitude higher than the concentration of Cyt c (10 μM) in bulk aqueous solution*. This is clear evidence that the irreversible IET wave is not simply due to reduction of Cyt *c*-Fe(III) by DcMFC, but instead due to electrocatalysis of O_2 reduction by Cyt *c* at pH 7 in the presence of DcMFC, as described in Fig. S16. In other words, *as Cyt c-Fe(III) acts as a catalyst, it is renewed at the interface during CV cycling and maintains a steady-state concentration*.

Fig. S16. Electrocatalysis of O_2 reduction by Cyt *c* at the electrified aqueous|organic interface in the presence of the electron donor DcMFC in the organic phase.

Another product of the interfacial electrocatalysis of O₂ reduction by Cyt *c* are DcMFC⁺ ions, which undergo reversible ion transfer at a negative potential (Fig. 4B). Using the Randles-Sevcik equation for reversible reactions:

$$i_p = (2.69 \times 10^5) (n^{\frac{3}{2}} D^{\frac{1}{2}} C A \nu^{\frac{1}{2}}) \quad (S7)$$

with the constant 2.69×10^5 given in C·mol⁻¹·V^{-1/2} diffusion coefficient of DcMFC in TFT (D) = 5.95×10^{-6} cm² s⁻¹ (35), $n = 1$ and $A = 1.53$ cm², the concentration of DcMFC⁺ ions generated during the first CV cycle were estimated as 177 μM, more than an order of magnitude higher than the initial concentration of Cyt *c*-Fe(III) in the aqueous phase. The latter again indicates electrocatalysis of O₂ reduction by Cyt *c* at pH 7 in the presence of DcMFC. Moreover, the concentrations of O₂ in water (0.25 mM) and the organic solvent (1.39 mM) are in the range of the experimentally indicated Cyt *c* concentration at the aqueous|organic interface.

S4.2 Analyses of double potential step chronoamperometry (DPSCA) data. The conclusions reached from the CV analyses *vide supra* were supported by coupling double potential step chronoamperometry (DPSCA), to highlight the large charge transfer taking place at positive potentials indicative of electrocatalysis, with *in situ* parallel beam UV/vis spectroscopy experiments, to monitor the interfacial Cyt *c*-Fe(II) concentration during IET (Fig. S17).

Fig. S17. (A) Double potential step chronoamperograms at positive (+0.4 V) and negative (−0.3 V) biasing using electrochemical cell 2 (see Fig. 5). (B) *In situ* parallel beam UV/vis absorbance spectra obtained with DPSCA.

For DPSCA, the initial step-potential was at +0.4V and held for 10 s. This positive potential was enough to start the IET reaction. Subsequently, the potential was changed to −0.3 V and held for another

10 s; the negative bias promotes DcMFC^+ ion transfer. A negative and positive step-potential represents a full cycle of 20 s, and this process was repeated for 300 cycles (Fig. S17A). A very significant charge transfer of 5.10×10^{-4} C was observed during the first 10 s of positive biasing (Fig. S17A, half-cycle 1) and attributed to the IET process since no background currents are expected in this potential region (see blank CVs in Fig. 2B-C and E). However, the integrated form of the Cottrell equation (a.k.a the Anson equation):

$$Q(t) = 2nFAC \sqrt{\frac{D_{\text{Cyt } c} t}{\pi}} \quad (\text{S8})$$

predicts a charge transfer of 4.45×10^{-6} C under our experimental conditions (see electrochemical cell 2 in Fig. 5). Thus, this chronoamperometric analysis aligns with the earlier CV data analysis and suggests that the Cyt *c* concentration at the electrified water|TFT interface must be two orders of magnitude larger than the bulk concentration.

In situ parallel beam UV/vis Soret absorbance measurements obtained using DPSCA monitored the reduction of Cyt *c*—Fe(III) directly above the interface, confirmed by the intensity and resolution of the α - and β -bands increasing (Fig. S17B, inset), as summarised also in Fig. 4A. However, the UV/vis spectra in Fig. S17B also clearly show that near the interface, the concentration of reduced Cyt *c*-Fe(II) did not change significantly with time, reaching a steady-state concentration. The latter is precisely what would be expected if Cyt *c* acts as an interfacial electrocatalyst of O_2 reduction, as described in Fig. S16.

Section S5 Interfacial electron transfer under anaerobic and aerobic conditions

Fig. S18. (A) The stability of the electron transfer signal indicates that the IET event under anaerobic conditions is mechanistically distinct from that in the presence of O_2 . (B) Scheme showing the most probable mechanism under anaerobic conditions where the electron exchange between face-to-face orientated Cyt *c* molecules must occur through their exposed heme edges. (C) Charge vs. time plot under aerobic (black line) and anaerobic (red line) conditions. (D) DcMfc⁺ ion transfer peak current vs. time under aerobic (black line) and anaerobic (red line) conditions. The progressive accumulation of Cyt *c* oligomers was slower under anaerobic conditions, as shown by the absence of any decrease in the DcMfc⁺ ion transfer peak current.

Section S6 *Ex situ* and *in situ* iodometric titration

Fig. S19. (A) Iodometric titration control experiment. A solution of potassium iodide (KI) is oxidised by adding an aliquot of H_2O_2 producing triiodide species. (B) *In situ* parallel beam UV/vis absorbance spectra using electrochemical cell 3 (see Fig. 5) in the absence of Cyt *c*; no triiodide bands were observed, meaning DcMFC alone as an electron donor does not produce detectable levels of H_2O_2 .

The iodometric titrations were performed by adding potassium iodide to the aqueous phase. When iodide is oxidised to triiodide by H_2O_2 under acidic conditions, it displays two characteristic absorption bands at 287 and 350 nm (Fig. S19A). These experiments were carried out at pH 2 due to the low oxidative strength of H_2O_2 towards triiodide production at pH 7. In the absence of Cyt *c*, no triiodide bands were recorded (Fig. S19B). This control experiment shows that in the absence of Cyt *c* as an interfacial catalyst, DcMFC does not reduce O_2 at the water|TFT interface at detectable concentrations.

Section S7 Differential capacitance measurements in the presence of different *c*-type cytochromes

Fig. S20. Differential capacitance measurements after 30 CV cycles in the presence of different *c*-type cytochromes at the water|TFT interface, see electrochemical cell 1 (Fig. 5).

At our liquid bio-interface, differential capacitance measurements after 30 CV cycles in the presence of Cyt *c*₁ showed a major drop in capacitance in comparison to Cyt *c* or Cyt *c*₅₅₂, characteristic of a zwitterionic phospholipid penetrating the aqueous|organic interface (Fig. S20). The PZC values of Cyt *c*, Cyt *c*₅₅₂ and Cyt *c*₁ all shifted negatively, and the positioning of the PZC of the group *c*-cytochromes converged at ca. 0.0 V.

Section S8 Cyclic voltammetry measurements in the presence of bovine serum albumin (BSA)

Fig. S21A dashed and red lines show BSA's interfacial voltammetry in the absence and presence of BSA, respectively. Repetitive cyclic voltammetry has shown that the electrochemistry of BSA at pH 7 is featureless at soft interfaces. Furthermore, we carried experiments with a mixture of 10 μ M BSA + 10 μ M Cyt *c* dissolved in the aqueous phase and DcMFC as the electron donor in the organic phase. The voltametric response shown in Fig. S21B was like the one reported in the main manuscript. Therefore, heme proteins such as Cyt *c* act as catalysts towards oxygen reduction reactions.

Fig. S21. Cyclic voltammetry in the presence of aqueous (A) bovine serum albumin (BSA) and (B) a mixture BSA + Cyt *c*. DcMFC was used as the organic electron donor as described in electrochemical cell 2 (see Fig 5).